

NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7255218>

Abstract: *Most of us is an ignorant organizer of Hakida we heard. Some people are non-governmental is the organizer of the hakida on the Bioja ega bursa, the chepilarn of the state is organized by Lay They didn't get it. In fact, the representative office is an organization of What, who, what, them intends to Kyrgyzstan has an answer to the question of how to organize, how to, and how to organize.*

Key words: non-state, non-profit, organizations, about

Pursuant to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations", a non-governmental non-commercial organization is a voluntary organization established by individuals and (or) legal entities, which does not make income (profit) the main goal of its activity, and receives income (profit) from its participants (is a self-governing organization that does not distribute among its members).

A non-governmental non-profit organization is a legal entity, an association established by citizens (legal entities) for the protection of their rights, joint realization of common interests, charity and other purposes. For example, in European countries, unionization of workers to protect their rights is one of the first manifestations of non-governmental non-profit organizations.

Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Non-governmental Non-profit Organizations" defines a non-governmental non-profit organization as follows:

A non-governmental non-profit organization is a self-governing organization established voluntarily by individuals and (or) legal entities, which does not make income (profit) the main goal of its activity and does not distribute the received income (profit) among its participants (members).

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A non-governmental non-profit organization is established to protect the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, other democratic values, to achieve social, cultural and educational goals, to satisfy spiritual and other intangible needs, to carry out charitable activities, and for other socially useful purposes.

We often come across names such as the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan, the Federation of Societies for the Protection of Consumer Rights of Uzbekistan, the Association of Business Women of Uzbekistan "Tadbirkor Ayl", the Federation of Uzbekistan "Uzbek Martial Arts". Most of us may not have a clear idea about them. Some consider these organizations to be state organizations, while others believe that they are a type of business. Of course, many of us citizens are aware that the above-mentioned organizations are a group of citizens or businessmen united to achieve mutual social, cultural and educational goals, to satisfy spiritual and other intangible needs, to carry out charitable activities and to achieve other socially useful results - non-governmental non-commercial organizations.

Therefore, in order to create a complete picture of the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, we will dwell on the concept of non-governmental non-profit organizations, the purposes for which they are formed, their activities and importance.

The activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations are generally regulated by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Non-governmental non-profit organizations". Special laws include the Law "On Public Associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Law "On Guarantees of the Activities of Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations", the Law "On Public Funds", the Law "On Political Parties", "On Trade Unions, Their Rights and Guarantees of their Activities". gi laws can be used as an example.

Article 2 of the Law "On Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations" defines the concept of a non-governmental non-profit organization as follows: a non-governmental non-profit organization is a voluntary organization established by individuals and (or) legal entities, which does not make income (profit) the main purpose of its activity, and receives the income is a self-governing organization that does not distribute (profits) among its participants (members)

As it can be seen from the given definition, the activities of NGOs are characterized by such features as separation from the state,

voluntariness, registration in a prescribed manner, non-profit making, and self-management.

Of course, the mutual association of individuals and legal entities does not automatically become a non-governmental non-profit organization. They will have the status of an NGO only after being registered in accordance with the law. Their activities are regulated on the basis of the charter approved by the founders (members) and the founding agreement concluded by the participants.

In addition, the registration conditions for certain types of NGOs are defined in the legislation. For example, a religious organization is established at the initiative of at least one hundred citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have reached the age of eighteen and are permanently living in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

USED LITERATURE:

1. https://andijon.adliya.uz/main/uz/interaktivnye-uslugi/sizning-savolingiz/title.php?ELEMENT_ID=11910
2. <https://lex.uz/docs/11360>
3. <https://parliament.gov.uz/uz/laws/adopted/96/3430/>

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